

Norway

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Norway, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system but complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the differences between types of higher education institutions in Norway are mainly related to their self-accreditation rights. Universities can without applying for external accreditation establish study programmes at all levels. University colleges may establish new programmes at the bachelor level without applying for accreditation. The state-owned colleges who have the right to award the degree Ph.D. may establish master programmes within the subject area of their Ph.D. Private higher education institutions accredited in one of the categories mentioned in Specific Legislative Framework have the same freedom of establishment of programmes as the state-owned institutions belonging to the same category, while the private higher education institutions without institutional accreditation still have to apply to NOKUT for all new programmes.

The different categories of higher education institutions in Norway are as follows:

- Universities
- Specialised university institutions (both public and private)
- University colleges (both public and private) including two public University colleges of arts
- Other university colleges (public, but not under the auspices Ministry of Education and Research, i.e. military colleges and the Norwegian Police University College)
- Higher education institutions that provide accredited study programmes (private).

In 2016 and 2017 several mergers took place in Norway and the Higher Education landscape has gone through major changes. Transfers between the institutions are encouraged and simplified by the degree system.

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/norway/types-higher-education-institutions>

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 below provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. All ten Universities (*Universitet*) in Norway are public institutions and have the right to award PhDs. Five of the seven public and all the private (government-dependent) Specialized university institutions (*Vitenskapelig høyskole m.fl.*) and the Academy of the art (*Kunsthøgskole*) are also all PhD awarding.

Complementarily, the five State university colleges (*Statlig høyskole*) and six Privates Colleges (*Privat høyskole*). While most of the *Statlig høyskole* award PhDs, their private counterparts do not. Military colleges (*Militær høyskole*) and State police academies (*Politihøgskole*), all of them public, do not award PhDs and play a more limited role in the Norwegian HEI system.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	Private government-dependent	PhD awarding
Academy of the art	Kunsthøgskole	1	1	0	0	1
Military college	Militær høyskole	1	1	0	0	0
Private college	Privat høyskole	5	0	0	5	0
Specialized university institution	Vitenskapelig høyskole m.fl.	10	7	1	2	8
State police academy	Politihøgskole	1	1	0	0	0
State university college	Statlig høyskole	5	5	0	0	4
University	Universitet	10	10	0	0	10
Total		33	25	1	7	23

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Norway's higher education and its evolution over time

Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of HEI population is relatively recent. While the University of Oslo, the oldest Norwegian university, dates back to 1811, no other HEI was founded before the

20th centuries. Overall, however, Norwegian HEIs are much younger; only four of the HEIs were founded before World War II and almost two thirds after 1990.

The figure shows two distinct patterns of expansion. First, the number (and size) of HEIs has been steadily increased after the second World War. The second wave of expansion was initiated in 1994 with the foundation of seven of today's HEIs. This process continues until today, almost two thirds of the HEIs were founded after 1994. Among the seven HEIs in ETER founded after 2009, two are Universities, two are State university colleges, two are Specialized university institutions and one is a Private college.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

However, the figure above only displays organisations that were independent at the end of the reported period, and it does not account for mergers and other demographic events. Several State university colleges and Private colleges were merged into Universities or Specialized university institutions between 2014 and 2017, reducing the total number of HEIs from 50 to 33. Most recently, in 2018 two former State university colleges were accredited as Universities (Oslo Metropolitan University and University of Southeast Norway).

Students

Universities account for 66% of the students enrolled. Public and Private Specialized university institution account for another 12% of total students. Complementarily, State university colleges and Privates colleges enrol one fifth of all students. However, the Private colleges enrol only 5% of the total students and, therefore, play a much smaller role in the national higher education system compared to their public counterparts enrolling 15%. The all other institutional types play a minor role in the aggregate (see Figure 2).

However, according to different institutional mandates, we also observe systematic differences between educational levels: Colleges account for 25% of the bachelor students but only 13% of the master students and 2% of doctorates. In contrast, Universities account for 92% of all PhD students.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 5-7

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there are major differences between HEIs in size, as measured by total personnel in full time equivalents (FTE), and in the personnel composition. Universities account for about 80% of total personnel in Norway, complemented by State university colleges (10%) and Specialized university institutions

(7%). As of the personnel composition, the share of support and administrative personnel is similar by type of HEIs between 34% and 40%. Research and teaching assistants are of very limited importance across all institutional types in Norway.

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT². Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e. career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As of Norway, data show a relatively flat hierarchy, with 26% of academic personnel at the junior level and 18% at the senior level. However, about one quarter of academic personnel is classified as “other seniority level”. The majority (57%) of junior academic personnel is female and intermediate personnel is almost exactly balanced in terms of gender, but only 33% of senior-level academic personnel are female (see Figure 4).

² OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Financial resources

As illustrated in Figure 5, in the year 2020, Universities account for almost 80% of financial revenues and about 80% of the academic personnel of the whole HEI system, which is substantially more than their share of students. This broadly corresponds to the fact that Universities also have an important research function. State university colleges account for another 10% of financial revenues and academic staff, which is less than their share of students.

The difference between Universities and State university college is also reflected in the composition of revenues displayed in Figure 6, where only Universities earn a large proportion of revenues from (research-related) third-party funds (20%). Overall, state allocation remains dominant for all institutional types in Norway, while student fees play a minor role and are only of relevancy for Private colleges and Specialized university institutions (not displayed in Figure 6)

Figure 5. Resources, academic personnel, and total students enrolled by type of HEI, 2020

Figure 6. Composition of resources by type of HEI, 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of students, data show a pattern of expansion in the number of enrolled students increasing by 30% from 2011 to 2020. This growth was similar across all institutional categories until 2014. However, caused by the reorganisation of the Norwegian HEI system (see section Institutional history) in the following years, a shift in the relative importance in terms of students enrolled can be observed. From 2015 to 2020 the number of students in State university colleges massively declined, reducing the share of total students enrolled at State university colleges from 38% to 15%. In turn, the share of Universities increased from 43% to 65% within five years. The number of students enrolled at the Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) increased due to this reorganisation by about 15,000 making it the largest Norwegian HEI in terms of students enrolled today. While the number of students continued to slightly increase in the most recent years, the shares of the remaining institutional categories have been stable over time.

Figure 7. Share of students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by , with an increase of 33% from 2011 to 2020, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in Norway’s HEIs kept pace with the increase in the number of students. Like for students, the reorganisation of the HEI system, is also reflected in an increasing concentration of academic personnel at Universities and a decreasing importance of the other institutional types.

Figure 8. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

Note: To keep consistency, the figure includes teaching and research assistants since these were included in academic personnel from 2017-2019.

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